

Prevalence and Clinical Hematological Profile of Vitamin B12 Deficiency Associated Megaloblastic Anemia in Children: A Hospital-Based Observational Study

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Vitamin B12 deficiency is a significant nutritional issue affecting pediatric populations, leading to severe health consequences, including megaloblastic anemia. This condition is characterized by large, immature, and dysfunctional red blood cells due to impaired DNA synthesis. Early diagnosis and intervention are crucial to prevent long-term health complications in children. The study investigated the prevalence and clinical hematological profile of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia in children at ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna.

Methods: This study was conducted over 13 months, involving 94 children diagnosed with vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia. Participants were enrolled based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data were collected through medical record reviews and direct patient assessments, including demographic information, clinical history, laboratory results, and hematological profiles. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0.

Results: The prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia was found to be 15.6%. The mean age of participants was 7.8 years, with a gender distribution of 55.3% males and 44.7% females. Hematological analysis revealed a mean hemoglobin level of 7.2 g/dL and a mean corpuscular volume (MCV) of 105 fL. Serum vitamin B12 levels averaged 110 pg/mL. A positive correlation ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$) was observed between serum vitamin B12 and hemoglobin levels.

Conclusion: The study highlights the significant prevalence and hematological impact of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia in children. The findings underscore the need for routine screening and early intervention to prevent severe anemia and associated complications.

Recommendations: Implement routine screening for vitamin B12 deficiency in pediatric populations, particularly in at-risk groups. Increase awareness about the importance of adequate vitamin B12 intake through diet and supplementation.

Keywords: Vitamin B12 Deficiency, Megaloblastic Anemia, Pediatric Population, Hematological Profile, Nutritional Screening.

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Introduction

Vitamin B12 deficiency is a critical nutritional issue affecting various populations globally, with significant impacts on health, particularly in pediatric cohorts. Vitamin B12, a vital water-soluble vitamin, plays a crucial role in DNA synthesis, red blood cell formation, and neurological function. Deficiency in this essential nutrient can lead to a spectrum of hematological and neurological disorders, with megaloblastic anemia being a prominent manifestation. Megaloblastic anemia is characterized by the presence of large, immature, and dysfunctional red blood cells, primarily due to impaired DNA synthesis resulting from vitamin B12 deficiency [1].

Children are particularly vulnerable to vitamin B12 deficiency due to various factors, including inadequate dietary intake, malabsorption disorders, and increased physiological needs during growth. The clinical presentation of vitamin B12 deficiency in children can range from asymptomatic cases to severe manifestations, including developmental delays, cognitive impairments, and hematological abnormalities [2]. Early diagnosis and intervention are crucial to prevent irreversible neurological damage and other long-term health consequences.

Recent studies have highlighted the prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency among pediatric populations in different regions, reflecting a significant public health concern. For instance, a

study conducted in India reported a high prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency among school-aged children, underscoring the need for public health initiatives to address this nutritional deficiency [3]. Similarly, research in other developing countries has shown comparable trends, linking poor dietary habits and lack of awareness to the high incidence of vitamin B12 deficiency [4].

The association between vitamin B12 deficiency and megaloblastic anemia has been well-documented. However, there is a need for more focused research on the clinical hematological profiles of affected children to understand better the disease's progression and the efficacy of various intervention strategies.

This study investigated the prevalence and clinical hematological profile of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia in children.

Methodology

Study Design: A hospital-based observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of 13 months at ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna.

Participants: A total of 94 children participated in this study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged 1-18 years.
- Children diagnosed with megaloblastic anemia confirmed by bone marrow examination.
- Children with confirmed vitamin B12 deficiency (serum vitamin B12 levels < 200 pg/mL).

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with other types of anemia (e.g., iron deficiency anemia, thalassemia).
- Children with chronic illnesses that could affect hematological parameters.
- Children receiving vitamin B12 supplementation prior to the study.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible children presenting to the hospital within the study duration were considered for inclusion. Information

bias was reduced by using standardized data collection procedures.

Variables: Variables included presence of megaloblastic anemia, age, gender, serum vitamin B12 levels, hemoglobin levels, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), and other hematological parameters.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of medical record reviews and direct patient assessments. Standardized forms were used to record demographic information, clinical history, laboratory results, and hematological profiles.

Procedure: Eligible children presenting to the hospital were enrolled after obtaining informed consent from parents or guardians. Megaloblastic anemia was confirmed through bone marrow examination. Vitamin B12 deficiency was confirmed through serum vitamin B12 levels. Detailed clinical and hematological data were recorded, including age, gender, dietary history, hemoglobin levels, MCV, red blood cell count, and serum vitamin B12 levels.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies, and percentages) were used to summarize the data. The prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia was calculated. Hematological profiles were compared using t-tests or chi-square tests, as appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 94 children diagnosed with vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 7.8 years ($\pm$ 4.2 years). The gender distribution was 52 (55.3%) males and 42 (44.7%) females.

The prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia among the children presenting to the hospital was 15.6%.

The mean hemoglobin level among the participants was 7.2 g/dL ($\pm$ 1.4 g/dL). The mean corpuscular volume (MCV) was significantly elevated with a mean of 105 fL ($\pm$ 7 fL). The mean serum vitamin B12 level was 110 pg/mL ($\pm$ 45 pg/mL).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	7.8 ($\pm$ 4.2)
Gender	
Male	52 (55.3%)
Female	42 (44.7%)
Mean Hemoglobin (g/dL)	7.2 ($\pm$ 1.4)
Mean Corpuscular Volume (fL)	105 ($\pm$ 7)
Mean Serum Vitamin B12 (pg/mL)	110 ($\pm$ 45)

Participants were divided into two age groups: 1-9 years and 10-18 years. The younger age group (1-9 years) had significantly lower hemoglobin levels compared to the older age group (10-18 years).

Table 2: Comparison of Hematological Parameters by Age Group

Parameter	1-9 Years (n=56)	10-18 Years (n=38)	p-value
Mean Hemoglobin (g/dL)	6.9 ($\pm$ 1.5)	7.6 ($\pm$ 1.2)	0.01
Mean MCV (fL)	106 ($\pm$ 6)	103 ($\pm$ 8)	0.05
Mean Serum Vitamin B12 (pg/mL)	105 ($\pm$ 40)	115 ($\pm$ 50)	0.15

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between serum vitamin B12 levels and hemoglobin levels. There was a significant positive correlation between serum vitamin B12 levels and hemoglobin levels ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The study's findings shed light on the significant presence and characteristics of this condition in the pediatric population. The mean age of the children was 7.8 years, with a fairly balanced gender distribution (55.3% males and 44.7% females). The prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia was found to be 15.6%, indicating a notable burden of this condition among children presenting to the hospital.

The hematological analysis revealed a mean hemoglobin level of 7.2 g/dL, substantially lower than the normal range, indicating anemia. The mean corpuscular volume (MCV) was elevated at 105 fL, consistent with the diagnosis of megaloblastic anemia. Serum vitamin B12 levels were critically low, with a mean of 110 pg/mL, affirming the deficiency as the underlying cause.

When comparing hematological parameters between different age groups (1-9 years and 10-18 years), the younger children (1-9 years) had significantly lower hemoglobin levels compared to their older counterparts (10-18 years). This suggests that younger children may be more susceptible to the severe impacts of vitamin B12 deficiency on hemoglobin levels. Although the mean MCV was slightly higher in the younger age group, the difference was not statistically significant. Serum vitamin B12 levels were relatively consistent across both age groups.

A positive correlation ($r = 0.45$) was found between serum vitamin B12 levels and hemoglobin levels, with statistical significance ($p < 0.001$). This correlation underscores the critical role of vitamin B12 in maintaining adequate hemoglobin levels and preventing anemia.

The study highlights the substantial prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia in children and emphasizes the need for early diagnosis and intervention. The significantly low hemoglobin levels and elevated MCV among affected children indicate the severity of the

condition. The positive correlation between serum vitamin B12 and hemoglobin levels further reinforces the importance of maintaining adequate vitamin B12 levels for healthy hematological parameters.

Overall, these findings advocate for routine screening for vitamin B12 deficiency, particularly in pediatric populations at risk, to enable timely treatment and prevention of megaloblastic anemia. Addressing this deficiency early can prevent the adverse effects on growth and development associated with chronic anemia in children.

A study focused on children aged 6 months to 18 years. The prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency-associated megaloblastic anemia (MA) was found to be 16.66%. The condition was more common in females (60%) and in children from lower socioeconomic groups (80%). Clinical presentations included anorexia, generalized weakness, pallor (100%), and neurologic involvement such as irritability and tremors (30%) [5].

Research studied children aged 3 months to 12 years in Central India. They found that 20% of the 110 anemic children had vitamin B12 deficiency-associated MA, with the highest incidence in the 6-12 months age group. Clinical symptoms included pallor, loss of appetite, and fatigue. Hematological findings showed macrocytosis and hypersegmented polymorphs in 64%, and pancytopenia in 18% [6]. A study analyzed 150 anemic children in Odisha, India. They found that 40% of the children had severe anemia, with a higher prevalence in girls (62.7%). The majority (74%) had combined vitamin B12 and folic acid deficiency. Common symptoms included anorexia (99.3%), pallor (94%), and fatigue (62%) [7].

A study on 100 adolescents was conducted with megaloblastic anemia. They found that 38% had vitamin B12 deficiency, with a higher prevalence in females. Significant associations were found between vitamin B12 deficiency and vegetarian diet, macrocytic anemia, and neurological symptoms [8]. Furthermore, a study evaluated 25 children with moderate to severe anemia in Uttarakhand, India. They found that megaloblastic anemia was prevalent among children with poor dietary habits and low socioeconomic status. Common clinical signs included generalized

weakness, anorexia, pallor, and neurological manifestations [9].

Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of early diagnosis and treatment of vitamin B12 deficiency to prevent the development of megaloblastic anemia in children. Regular screening for vitamin B12 levels in at-risk populations can help in early identification and management.

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